

Natural User Interfaces in the Field of Human-Robot Interaction Using Haptic Devices

Francisco J. Rodríguez-Sedano^{a,*}, Camino Fernández-Llamas^b, Miguel A. Conde-González^b, Gonzalo Esteban-Costales^b

^a*Department of Electric, Systems and Automatics Engineering, School of Engineering, Campus Vegazana, University of León, 24071, León, Spain.*

^b*Department of Mechanics, Computer Science and Aeronautics, School of Engineering, Campus Vegazana, University of León, 24071, León, Spain.*

Abstract

When considering the application of different interfaces for human-robot interaction, several questions about their usability arise: Which are the most appropriate interfaces for this type of interaction? Can haptic devices improve human-robot interaction? Are there any type of interface that is not suitable for interacting with robots? This study is concentrated on the use of natural interfaces in the context of human-robot interaction that employ haptic devices. An extensive search of the literature was performed in order to locate methodologies, methods and/or metrics to evaluate the usability of these types of interfaces.

During the course of the study the difficulty of assessing the usability of the interfaces employed in human-robot interaction was confirmed. The fact was particularly true when the interfaces involved more than one type of interaction with users (multimodal user interfaces). The results obtained made it possible to state that the use of natural interfaces in the context of human-robot interactions brings with it a major enhancement, especially when haptic devices are employed.

Keywords: Natural User Interfaces, Human-robot Interaction, Systematic Literature Review, Haptic Devices

*Corresponding author

Email address: francisco.sedano@unileon.es (Francisco J. Rodríguez-Sedano)

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2641574>

1. Introduction

Over the course of the last ten years or so, interactions with equipment have tended to be performed primarily through data acquisition interfaces bringing into play devices such as a mouse, joystick, keyboard, or remote sensors. More recently, there has been a move to integrate these items for data acquisition with output devices, through the use of combined interfaces such as touch screens, touch pads, and similar equipment.

According to Montuschi et al. (2014), at the present day the main trends in user interfaces (UI) are the following: 1) Input devices involving the sense of touch by using multiple contact points (touch and multi-touch screens); 2) Inertial reference (Wii remote or “Wiimote”) or movement capture (Kinect) systems; 3) Tangible interfaces (gesture recognition, wearable input devices); and 4) Natural user interfaces (eye tracking glasses, Leap Motion sensors, smart-watches, haptic devices, etc.). This study will concentrate on the last one of these categories.

Natural user interfaces (NUIs) arose within the context of human-computer interaction (HCI), but through their intrinsic philosophy they fit perfectly into the field of human-robot interaction (HRI). A natural interaction with robots can be considered as an extension of interacting with computers in general. In order to obtain a more natural way of interaction, the sense of touch should be considered, together with sight, as one of the main senses involved. Haptic technology provides to the sense of touch the same feedback that computer graphics provide to the sense of sight [Srinivasan and Basdogan (1997)]. For this reason, the user perception of the interaction can be significantly enhanced.

In the field of HRI there are a number of pieces of work in which haptic interfaces have been used. This type of device is already being used to control robots and also for learning, with applications for training motor capabilities, rehabilitation and social interaction, as may be seen in the works by Salter et al. (2006) and Stiefelhagen et al. (2004).

It is also important to stress that touch plays a major role in human social life. This is because it is through this sense that positive or negative emotions are communicated. Additionally, it is an intensifier of emotions in interpersonal communication. Certain haptic interfaces and tactile devices might enable users to improve their abilities to communicate emotions, thus adding a further dimension to communication, as stated by Brave and Dahley (1997) and Haans and IJsselsteijn (2006).

Hence, it can be stated that one emerging area of research is the study of what has been termed "Affective Haptics", as reflected in investigations by Haans et al. (2007). This is centred on the design of devices and systems that can trigger, enhance, or influence the emotional state of an individual by means of the sense of touch. Human emotions can easily be evoked by various different signals, and the sense of touch is one of the most emotion-laden channels. The type of device has great potential for on-line contexts that facilitate remote contact with other people, such as teleconferencing, recovery, or treatment of individuals with problems of mental, emotional, social and physical sorts [Tsetsserukou (2010)].

The present paper is intended to provide an extensive systematic review of the literature with the aim of exploring ways of measuring the usability of NUIs in the context of HRI, especially when haptic devices are used. This study will support the next step in our research. On the one hand, we have already developed a framework for creating haptic simulators as teaching/learning tools [Gonzalo Esteban (2015)]. On the other hand, a research line is focussed on studying the interaction with robots [Matellán and Fernández (2014)]. Our goal involves evaluating possible solutions for interacting with robots by means of haptic devices.

The article is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the method used for the review. Section 3 presents and discusses the results obtained from the review, while Section 4 considers its possible limitations. Finally, Section 5 presents the conclusions drawn and suggests future lines of research.

2. Research method

The method used for this article is based on proposals put forward by Cooper (1988) in his study. Hence, the principal topic and aims of the study were fixed, research questions were established that this review would attempt to answer and criteria were set up on the basis of which articles picked out in the various search phases were to be included or excluded. Finally, an analysis was undertaken of the results emerging from the review. Figure 1 shows, in a schematic form, the various stages of the review that will be detailed later in the following sections of this paper.

Figure 1: Stages of review protocol.

The aim was thus to integrate, analyse and synthesize results to identify the

problems that can arise from employing user interfaces in the context of HRI when haptic devices are involved. This would allow new proposals to be made and hence, if possible, to improve interactions.

However, before any investigation was undertaken the following questions were addressed:

1. What was the period of time that this review should cover?
2. Was there any prior systematic review of the topic?

In response to the first question, it was decided that the most suitable time period for the study would be the last decade. It was felt that in the field of HCI there might be some earlier references, but in the areas of HRI, haptic interactions and natural interfaces, any article published before 2004 would be unlikely to reflect the state of the art in the sense in which it was intended to investigate it.

In respect of the second question, it is the case that systematic reviews are a very common practice in other sciences, such as Natural Sciences and Medicine. However, in the specific areas of Computer Science and Engineering, what was found were the following references within the field of software engineering: Jørgensen (2004), Jørgensen and Shepperd (2007), Dybå and Dingsøy (2008a), Kitchenham et al. (2009), Kitchenham et al. (2010), Chen and Babar (2011b), Wen et al. (2012) and Zhang and Babar (2013).

It also proved possible to find some systematic reviews directly linked to HRI, as can be seen from Table 1, although these reviews do not directly address the issues involved in present project. One noteworthy example is the survey undertaken by Riek (2012) of the use of Wizard of Oz (WoZ) methodology in this field, although it is a review based on very limited sources. Its aim was to contribute to general knowledge among the HRI community of the use of WoZ methods as an experimental technique, simplifying the employment of this methodology.

Ref.	Topic	Venue	Citation
Dautenhahn (2007)	Study about challenges of Human-Robot Interaction	International Journal of Advanced Robotic Systems	5
Prewett et al. (2010)	Managing workload in human-robot interaction	Computers in Human Behavior	16
Riek (2012)	Wizard of Oz Studies in HRI	Journal of Human-Robot Interaction	41
Barreto and Benitti (2012)	Study with quantitative evidence of the use of robotics in schools	Computers & Education	30
Bemelmans et al. (2012)	Socially Assistive Robots in Elderly Care	Journal of the American Medical Directors Association	37
Basteris et al. (2014)	Training modalities in robot-mediated rehabilitation	Journal of NeuroEngineering and Rehabilitation	10

Table 1: Systematic reviews in human-robot interaction.

Hence, the conclusion was that it was necessary for there to be a systematic review prior to any other research work. The reasons may be observed in the diagram shown as Figure 2, taken from work by Pautasso (2013). The need for such a survey is demonstrated in the upper left quarter of this graph, which shows that the number of reviews of the topic covered by the present paper is considerably smaller than the number of pieces of research work published in this area.

Figure 2: A conceptual diagram of the need for different types of literature reviews depending on the amount of published research papers and literature reviews.

The present work was intended to provide a report on the results of a study performed by a combination of several methods used in the systematic literature

reviews referred above. Details of the various stages in the research method chosen are provided in the sections below.

2.1. Research questions

The purpose of this review was to identify and describe the knowledge about the use of natural interfaces in the context of HRI when haptic devices are employed that could be found in the relevant literature. This was done through a principal question: Can natural interfaces improve human-robot interaction when haptic devices are used?

This question had two perspectives. The first considered the type of interfaces used in HRI when haptic devices are employed and their usability. The second perspective was intended to identify possible improvements in HRI thanks to the use of natural interfaces. This in turn could be broken down into various different angles: making HRI more effective, making it “more human”, improving user perceptions, and so forth. This was the most important dimension of the study.

In order to undertake the review on the basis of the principal question, the following research questions were addressed:

- **RQ1. Which types of interface are used in human-machine interaction and which are commonest in HRI?** It is of interest to learn what user interfaces are currently employed, as also which of them are most frequently utilized in the specific case of human-robot interaction.
- **RQ2. How can these interfaces be improved so that HRI becomes more effective?** Once it was known what types of interface are used in HRI, it would become of interest to discover whether these interfaces could be improved so that interaction would become more effective. It would also be of value to check if the use of more than one channel has any effect and the methods for evaluating the usability of such interfaces.

- **RQ3. What benefits might ensue from using natural interfaces in HRI when haptic devices are employed?** This final question would investigate in what way natural interfaces might improve human-robot interaction when haptic devices were in play.

2.2. Search strategy

The search procedure could be divided into various stages, as indicated by Brereton et al. (2007) in their work.

1. Identification of potentially suitable articles.
 - (a) Setting restrictions relating to the language of publication.
 - (b) Deciding from which sources primary studies should be obtained.
 - (c) Gathering titles and abstracts of potentially useful primary studies.
2. Selection of suitable articles.
 - (a) Applying criteria for inclusion and exclusion to the titles and abstracts collected.
 - (b) Getting potentially suitable whole articles on the basis of eligible titles and abstracts, and applying criteria for inclusion and exclusion to these.
 - (c) Assessing consistency in the selection of items.

This section will concentrate on the identification of relevant articles. This was done by selecting sources of information, building up search terms and executing a search process in accordance with a well-defined strategy that will be described in more detail below. Section 2.3 goes on to outline the next stage in selection.

2.2.1. Literature resources

When deciding which sources of information were to be incorporated in the study, it was crucial to start by weighing up whether any restriction should be applied in respect of language of publication. For practical reasons, the commonest approach is to include only publications in English and in the native

language of the author of any review, which in this case would be Spanish. However, some authors have stated that the quality of research is not necessarily tied to the language of publication, for instance Sandford (1996) in his work in this area. On the other hand, restrictions on language might skew the results of a systematic review by excluding publications that could be of relevance.

Moreover, it would appear reasonable to bring in only those items that had been published in specialist and indexed journals with a significant impact factor. It can be argued that such articles, having got through a process of peer review, are the most reliable. It is true that work with inconclusive or negative results is less likely to be published, regardless of its quality, so that its exclusion may skew the results of any review. This is what some authors have termed publication bias, and in some instances it leads to the exclusion from systematic reviews of unpublished pieces of work that might nevertheless be of very great interest for the aims of such surveys, as Tramèr et al. (1997) showed in his work.

The next step was to decide where to look for primary studies. At the present day the most widely used strategy is to search electronic databases. However, this is not a simple strategy, since on occasions there are overlaps between databases, and at other times many of the journals included in a given database are not taken into consideration by others, as was shown by Dickersin et al. (1994) in an article on the topic.

Moreover, searching for items exclusively in electronic databases may not be the best course, depending upon which topic is under investigation. Thus, searches should not merely cover electronic databases but should include detailed scrutiny of relevant journals. They should also look at what is called “grey literature” (bibliographic references, doctoral theses, papers delivered at conferences, reports by public or private institutions, unpublished work or items appearing in journals that are not indexed, as well as other sources not formally published), as suggested by Conn et al. (2003) in work on this point.

In either case, for operational reasons the selection of potentially eligible articles is normally done by identifying titles and abstracts. Nonetheless, every

database has its own particular structure, and uses its own criteria for indexation and keywords that are more or less specific to it. Obviously, authors of reviews must become familiar with these, as can be seen from work by Dieste and Padua (2007).

For the present investigation, searches were to concentrate on the following sources (see Table 2).

Type	Source	Acronym
JOURNALS	Journal of Human-Robot Interaction	JHRI
	Advances in Information Systems and Technologies	AIST
	Journal on Multimodal User Interfaces	JMUI
	International Journal of Computer Applications	IJCA
	Journal of Human-Robot Interaction	JHRI
	International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology	IJCSIT
	ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction	ACM HCI
	IEEE Transactions on Robotics	IEEE TR
	IEEE Transactions on Human-Machine Systems	IEEE THMS
	IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement	IEEE TIM
PROCEEDINGS	ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-Robot Interaction	ACM HRI
	ACM SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems	ACM CHFCS
	ACM User Interface Software and Technology Symposium	ACM UIS
	International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces	ICIUI
	International Conference On Systems Engineering and Modeling	ICSEM
	IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation	IEEE ICRA
	IEEE International Symposium in Robot and Human Interactive Communication	IEEE ISRHIC
	IEEE Haptics Symposium	IEEE HAPTICS
	IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics	IEEE ROBIO
	International Conference on Human System Interaction	HSI
	DATABASE	Scopus
Taylor and Francis Online		T&F
Web of Science		WOS
ScienceDirect Web Editions		SDWEB
INTERNET	SpringerLink	SPL
	CiteSeerX	CITSEER
	WorldWideScience.org	WWSCIENCE
	e-Revistas	e-REV

Table 2: Literature resources used in this review.

The application of the search strategy to the various sources quoted above would provide a large number of bibliographic references, some of which might be duplicated. Thus, it would prove very useful in this phase to put into play

software for automated management of bibliographic citations, for example, ProCite ¹, EndNote ² or RefWorks ³.

2.2.2. Search terms

The investigation undertook searches both in Spanish and in English, although in the end the study included only those articles written in English. The terms utilized in the various searches depended on the research question being addressed, though in many instances these were shared. In particular, searches were made for the following terms:

- "Human-machine interfaces", either alone or in combination with the term "human-computer interaction" (*Human machine interfaces OR human computer interaction*).
- "Human robot interaction", combined with "multimodal interfaces" (*Human robot interaction AND multimodal interfaces*).
- "Natural user interfaces", whether on its own or combined with "touch" and "haptic devices", (*Natural user interfaces AND touch OR haptic devices*).

In building up the search strings for the various different libraries, the terms listed above were combined using the Boolean AND operator, for example:

```
<<(human machine interfaces OR human computer interaction) AND (Human robot  
interaction AND multimodal interfaces) AND (Natural user interfaces AND touch OR  
haptic devices)>>
```

However, because of the variable nature of the search services and the built-in functions of the electronic libraries investigated, it became clear that it was not possible to use a single search string for all the bibliographic sources. For

¹<http://www.procite.com/>

²<https://endnote.com/>

³<https://www.refworks.com/>

example, in searching the ACM Digital Library, it was necessary to build up various search strings in order to seek items on a basis that could be considered equivalent to other sources (like IEEE Xplore or Science Direct). Other researchers, such as Dybå et al. (2007), have also reported similar problems when using the ACM Digital Library for systematic reviews. Hence, the decision was taken to design and use different search strings for different sources.

Some authors, such as Chen and Babar (2011a) y Dybå et al. (2007), consider these variations the mechanisms used by the search engines available as one of the limitations on carrying out systematic reviews in software engineering. However, an attempt was made to ensure that the search strings utilized were logically and semantically equivalent, especially when it did not prove possible to use syntactically identical search strings for all the databases consulted.

A decision was also made to carry out a search prior to the review so as to determine the format and general presentation of the literature relating to the topic. This also was intended to choose the best strategy for extracting and compiling data. This search was performed with IEEE Xplore ⁴, Science Direct ⁵, CiteseerX ⁶, and Google Scholar ⁷.

A further crucial decision was to establish to which fields it was appropriate to apply the search string, which in the end were title, abstract and full text. It was considered that searching only the “title” field would not necessarily find every relevant publication, even if it was sufficient for a prior trawl. Thus, the “abstract” or “full text” fields should be included as well, although this was done in different search or selection phases, as will be seen later.

It can be stated that for the purposes of this research an item would be selected as a candidate if its title or abstract contained the keywords defined in the search string. In a later phase the full text of the pieces of work selected would also be scrutinized.

⁴<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home.jsp>

⁵<http://www.sciencedirect.com/>

⁶<http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/index>

⁷<https://scholar.google.com/>

2.2.3. Search process

In the light of the above, once decisions had been taken as to sources of information to consult, restrictions to apply and search terms to use, it was time to define a search strategy and commence review. As may be seen in Figure 3, adapted from Wen et al. (2012) work, two main processes were distinguished, search and selection, and each of these was split into two phases.

As for the search processes employed in the investigation, the following steps were taken, specified as two phases and shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Search and selection process.

- *Search Phase 1*: This involved individual searching in the electronic databases selected previously and then gathering together the articles proffered to constitute a set of candidate documents.
- *Search Phase 2*: This entailed scanning the references lists of the relevant articles so as to find further documents that might also be considered significant and then, where appropriate, adding them to the former set.

It should be emphasized that in order to cover all publications of interest

the following electronic libraries, that are important to this research, were used:

- ACM Digital Library ⁸.
- IEEE Xplore Digital Library.
- Science Direct.
- Web Of Science (WOS) ⁹.

It may be observed from Figure 3 that in the first search phase, after the elimination of duplicate entries and grouping of the articles, a total of 1,044 documents were noted that could be seen as candidates.

In view of this large number of documents emerging from the initial search phases, it was decided to use software that would permit them to be registered and classified for the selection phases and inclusion and exclusion criteria to be applied. The software chosen was *I, Librarian*¹⁰ (see Figure 4). This package is a file manager that allows researchers, academics and students to create a collection of articles in PDF format. The software is also an advanced tool that permits cataloguing, annotation, browsing and rapid searching of bibliographic references and PDF files. It is even able to search for PDF files on the basis of scanned images. Moreover, data can be exported from articles in various formats: EndNote, Research Information Systems (RIS), BibTex and Comma Separated Values (CSV).

⁸<http://dl.acm.org/>

⁹<http://apps.webofknowledge.com>

¹⁰<https://i-librarian.net/>

Figure 4: Screenshot software used to organize documents.

In this phase care was taken to ensure that searches in the databases included those newspapers, journals and conference proceedings that had been selected as sources of information. However, no secondary investigations following up references from all the primary sources were undertaken, since such secondary searches based on the bibliographies in items retrieved during the primary searches would have required an immense amount of resources.

At a later stage, and after the first selection phase described in the following section, there was a second search phase. At this point, these lists of references from articles considered relevant were scrutinized, so that where applicable they could be added to the set of documents chosen (see Figure 3).

2.3. Study selection

In view of the large number of articles that might possibly provide information of use in handling the research questions posed by this review, more than one filtering was needed to identify truly relevant articles. It was this

precisely that was the objective in the item selection procedure. Specifically, as illustrated in Figure 3, the process of selecting items was made up of two phases, which were:

- *Selection Phase 1*: This phase applied the inclusion and exclusion criteria (as defined below) to candidate pieces of work so as to identify relevant articles that would provide the data for answering the research questions posed at the start of the study.
- *Selection Phase 2*: This phase applied quality assessment criteria (defined in the next section) to relevant documents with the aim of choosing those of acceptable quality for later use in extracting data.

To refine the results of the first search phase, inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined for application to the various documents. To this end, their titles, or in some cases, their abstracts were scrutinized to allow a decision as to whether they met the inclusion criteria, or whether on the contrary they should be excluded from further study.

The criteria for inclusion were:

- Touching on one or more of the terms listed above relative to the topics comprised in the research questions, having a suitable structure, and proposing some sort of implementation initiative.
- Touching on one or more of the terms listed above relative to the topics comprised in the research questions, having a suitable structure, and putting forward coherent conclusions of a technological, pedagogical or methodological nature.
- Undertaking a critical review of one or more of the terms listed above relative to the topics comprised in the research questions.

For their part, the exclusion criteria were:

- Articles that although are not well grounded, did include the searching terms (in data bases or bibliographical references).

- Articles that included the terms mentioned, but only to redefine general concepts.
- Articles that covered the topic area and included the search terms, but in some other way did not match the research questions.

Application of these criteria during the first selection phase, led to the picking out of 134 relevant items. More detailed study of these articles and examination of bibliographic references in certain of them (Search Phase 2), led to a further 14 documents being added to the list of suitable items.

This selection of 148 articles was then submitted to further filtering in a second selection phase, on the basis of quality criteria which will be described hereafter. In this phase it was not merely the title and abstract that were looked at, but also the full text that was submitted to deeper consideration.

2.4. Assessment of Item Quality

During a systematic review, each item should be subjected to an evaluation of its quality with the aim of identifying those documents which match the main purpose of the review. This also allows an assessment of the impact of the quality of primary studies on the conclusions drawn from the systematic review.

There are various ways of performing such an assessment, but the choice was made to use a method specified by Wen et al. (2012) in their work. This involved evaluation of the quality of pieces of work in respect of their capacity and suitability for answering the research questions being considered and with regard to their possible impact on their conclusions to be drawn from the present study.

Hence, the decision was made to use quality assessment criteria adapted from those developed by Dybå et al. (2007). These may be seen in summary form in the following Table.

QUALITY CRITERIA

1.	Is the paper based on research or is it merely a report based on expert opinion)?
2.	Is there a clear statement of the aims of the research?
3.	Is there a description of the context in which the research was carried out?
4.	Was the research design appropriate to address the aims of the research?
5.	Was the recruitment strategy appropriate to the aims of the research?
6.	Was there a control group with which to compare treatments?
7.	Was the data collected in a way that addressed the research issue?
8.	Was the data analysis sufficiently rigorous?
9.	Is there a clear statement of findings?
10.	Is the study of value for research or practice?

Table 3: Quality criteria used in this review.

These criteria can be grouped into three main categories relating to quality that would be kept in mind when evaluating the pieces of work identified in the review. According to Dybå and Dingsøy (2008b), these qualities are rigour, credibility and relevance.

The first three quality criteria utilized had to do with the justification for the piece of work, its aims and its context.

The next five criteria referred to the rigour of the methods used in the research so as to establish the validity of the tools for data collection, methods of analysis and reliability of results.

In addition, a further criterion was added, relating to assessment of the credibility of the study methods utilized, so as to ensure that the conclusions were valid and significant.

The final criterion was related to evaluation of the relevance of the piece of work for the aims of the present research project.

Taken as a whole, these ten quality criteria provided a measurement of the degree to which it was possible to be sure that the conclusions of the item would offer a valuable contribution to the systematic review.

It should also be highlighted that the evaluation of the quality of the items chosen followed the same lines established in Chen and Babar (2011a) systematic review. A scale was used that assessed the quality of the items reviewed as one of only three possible grades (“YES”, “PARTLY” or “NO”) for each of the quality criteria established. These grades were quantified as scores by assigning a value of 1 for “YES”, 0.5 for “PARTLY” and 0 for “NO”.

Finally, to guarantee the reliability of the results of the review, only those relevant items that had an acceptable quality were considered for extracting and analysing data as described in the following sections. This was deemed to require a quality rating over 5.5 (55% of the maximum score). In consequence, of the 148 articles, 97 documents (65.54%) were rejected, as having a quality score below 5 in the second selection phase (see Table 4).

Quality level	N. of studies	Percent
VERY HIGH ($8.5 \leq \text{score} \leq 10$)	9	6.08
HIGH ($7 \leq \text{score} \leq 8$)	32	21.62
MEDIUM ($5.5 \leq \text{score} \leq 6.5$)	10	6.76
LOW ($3 \leq \text{score} \leq 5$)	75	50.68
VERY LOW ($0 \leq \text{score} \leq 2.5$)	22	14.86
TOTAL	148	100

Table 4: Quality levels of relevant studies.

As a last step, 51 documents (almost 28%) were identified and selected for data extraction in the next stage.

2.5. Data Extraction and Analysis

Once the items that met the quality criteria established in the previous Section (see Appendix A) had been selected, the next step was to extract data from these pieces of work so as to answer the research questions.

Hence, the following data were obtained from each document:

- The type of user interface in use.

- The domain and type of user.
- The method for evaluating the usability of the interface, if specified.
- Possible improvements in the use of the interface.

In order to investigate in an adequate manner the information extracted, there was a need for a quantitative analytic method that was appropriate and applicable to the data gathered.

Of the various methods available, the choice was made to use the so-called constant comparison method, described in work by Seaman (1999). This was a technique that appeared particularly suitable when data were context-sensitive, as was the case here. For example, an item mentioning the term “haptic interface” was deemed to be characteristic of user interfaces. Unless there was an understanding of the context in which this term was mentioned, it would not be possible to decide whether the piece of work dealt with points that were required for the item to be considered valid for the purposes of the research project.

In order to bring this method into play, it was very useful to assign codes to the documents selected, this coding making explicit the criteria on the basis of which characteristics of the items were coded. This phase was felt to be of importance in checking which characteristics of the pieces of work could have an impact on results. However, this was a tedious task and consumed a great deal of time and human resources.

In performing it, the following protocol proposed by Lincoln and Guba (1985):

- *Filling-in*: Each item was carefully read in detail and codes were added for fragments and elements related to one another in the various documents. This stage entailed reconstruction of the coding scheme whenever a new way of checking the different sources of information emerged.
- *Extension*: Where necessary, previously coded materials were revisited,

with new forms, topics or relationships being used to extract fresh information and code it.

- *Bridging*: If any new relationships or relationships that could not be understood within a given level or category were found, a record was made of them.
- *Surfacing*: New categories were identified that contained the previously created codes.

To ensure the reliability of the process of coding characteristics of items, especially in view of their complexity for recording and coding, two researchers from the group coded pieces of work independently and the degree of agreement between the codes assigned. This was in accordance with suggestions put forward by Orwin and Vevea (2009) in their book. For this purpose one of the features of the *I'Librarian* software was used, allowing annotations to be made in the PDF files themselves and the establishing of personalized categories that other authorized users could employ (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Screenshot software used for encoding the selected studies.

Each document was first coded by the two researchers independently. The results were shared to check whether there were any differences, so that the

coding outcomes could be improved. This process was repeated until a high level of agreement was reached (this was deemed to be $> 90\%$). All the articles remaining under consideration were finally given a definitive coding by the first author.

This coding process ended the stages of the review protocol adopted for this project.

3. Results and discussion

This section presents and discusses the results emerging from the review undertaken. Firstly, an overview is given of the items selected. Secondly, the results of the quality assessment for these are considered. Thereafter, the results of the review are presented and analysed in accordance with the research questions posed, each one being assigned a separate subsection.

3.1. General Overview

The study identified 51 relevant documents in the field of natural interfaces in HRI that had been published during the period running between 2004 and 2014 (see Figure 6). From the distribution of these items by year of publication shown in the figure, it may be observed that the number of pieces of research grew from 2010 onwards, this being explained by the steady increase in the use of haptic devices in the context of HRI. In 2014 the number of publications shows an apparent fall, but this was due to the fact that the search phase and selection were brought to a close in August of that year.

Figure 6: Number of publications per year.

The places of publication and the distribution of the items chosen are shown in Table 5. A glance at these details makes it possible to state that the literature on this research topic is widely spread over a range of publications. Thus, as can be seen from the table, the documents finally picked out appeared in no fewer than 32 different publications. There were 22 sources in which just one article was published (43%) and only three sources in which more than one, and up to four articles appeared (6%). Of the items selected, 51% were published in conference proceedings (26 out of 51), 47% in academic journals (24 out of 51) and only one came out in a book. It was also striking that some 20% of the articles chosen appeared in journals specializing in fields very distant from HRI and robotics, such as biomedicine. This fact reflects the multidisciplinary nature of the study.

Publication venue	Type	N. of studies	Percent
ACM Engineering Interactive Computing Systems (ACM EICS)	Conference	1	2.0%
ACM SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (ACM CHFCS)	Conference	2	3.9%
ACM User Interface Software and Technology Symposium (ACM UIS)	Conference	4	7.8%
ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-Robot Interaction (ACM HRI)	Conference	3	5.9%
Advanced Robotics (AR)	Journal	1	2.0%
Advances in Information Systems and Technologies (AIST)	Journal	1	2.0%
Autonomous Robots (AROB)	Journal	1	2.0%
Computer and Education (C&E)	Journal	1	2.0%
Computer and Graphics (C&G)	Journal	1	2.0%
Computer Animation and Virtual Worlds (CAVW)	Journal	1	2.0%
Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine (CMPB)	Journal	3	5.9%
Entertainment Computing (ECOM)	Journal	1	2.0%
Human-Computer Systems Interaction (AISC)	Book	1	2.0%
IEEE Transactions on Mechatronics (IEEE TOM)	Conference	1	2.0%
IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics (IEEE ROBIO)	Conference	1	2.0%
IEEE International Symposium on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (IEEE RHIC)	Conference	4	7.8%
IEEE Transactions on Haptics (IEEE HAPTICS)	Conference	2	3.9%
IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics (IEEE TIE)	Conference	1	2.0%
IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement (IEEE TIM)	Journal	1	2.0%
IEEE Transactions on Robotics (IEEE TR)	Conference	3	5.9%
International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces (ICIUI)	Conference	2	3.9%
International Gesture Workshop (IGW)	Conference	1	2.0%
International Journal of Computer Applications (IJCA)	Journal	1	2.0%
International Journal of Human-Computer Studies (IJHCS)	Journal	1	2.0%
Journal of Human-Robot Interaction (JHRI)	Journal	4	7.8%
Journal of Intelligent Service Robotics (JISR)	Journal	1	2.0%
Journal of Neuroscience Methods (JNM)	Journal	1	2.0%
Journal on Multimodal User Interfaces (JMUI)	Journal	2	3.9%
Motion in Games International Conference (MIG)	Conference	1	2.0%
Proceedings of the IEEE (IEEE PROC)	Journal	1	2.0%
Robotica (ROB)	Journal	1	2.0%
Robotics and Autonomous Systems (RAS)	Journal	1	2.0%
TOTAL		51	100

Table 5: Publication venues and distribution of selected studies.

3.2. Methodological quality

As was mentioned in Section 2.4, the decision was taken to assess each of the 51 items selected on the basis of the ten features in the quality criterion list (presented in Table 3). Two researchers from the group participating in the review, together with the main author, undertook individual evaluations of the quality of the relevant documents. At a later stage, meetings of the entire group

of researchers were held to discuss the outcomes of these quality assessments, with a final consensus being reached. The results may be seen in Table 6.

In respect of the quality of the items selected, the average rating out of a maximum 10 points was 7.62, implying a high level of quality.

In this review, all the articles chosen were pieces of research. However, there was one item which did not clearly present the aims of the investigation undertaken, so that under the second criterion it was given the "*PARTLY*" grade.

All the pieces of work had some form of description of the context in which the research had been done. However, in some instances this description was not sufficiently clear. Thus, 19.6% of the items were assigned a "*PARTLY*" grade.

Practically all the pieces of work provided a description of the research design used. Notwithstanding this, 56.86% gave no justification for the design adopted, so that they received a grade of "*PARTLY*". There were four items that did not give an adequate account of their data collection strategies, and only 29.42% explained how and why data had been identified and gathered. The remaining items were graded "*PARTLY*".

Similarly, just three pieces of work were found to have included one or more control groups, although a further seven employed user trials, and so received the "*PARTLY*" grade. As for descriptions of the data gathering protocol, every one of the items chosen did incorporate some details, although only 31.37% of the pieces of work gave an explanation of this protocol. In respect of the data analysis system, just six items provided an explanation or justification of the methods used; the remainder (86.27%) merely described it.

Finally, it should be noted that all the items chosen presented a clear description of the results of the research done. However, 23.53% had no discussion of them in relation to the research questions posed in the present study, so that they were graded "*PARTLY*".

Consideration of the average values in Table 4, with the exception of the first three criteria and the last, showed there was a significant gap here (especially

ID	QA1	QA2	QA3	QA4	QA5	QA6	QA7	QA8	QA9	QA10	Score
	Research	Aim	Context	R. design	Sampling	Ctrl. Grp.	Data coll.	Data ana.	Findings	Value	
[S01]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0	7.0
[S02]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	6.5
[S03]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S04]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S05]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.5
[S06]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.5	0	1.0	1.0	6.5
[S07]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	9.0
[S08]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	7.0
[S09]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S10]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.5
[S11]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.5
[S12]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	9.5
[S13]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0	6.5
[S14]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0	7.0
[S15]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S16]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S17]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	7.5
[S18]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0	7.0
[S19]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S20]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.0	7.5
[S21]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	7.5
[S22]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.0	6.5
[S23]	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	0.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0	7.0
[S24]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	7.0
[S25]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S26]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S27]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	7.5
[S28]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	7.0
[S29]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	7.0
[S30]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.0	6.5
[S31]	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.5	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	7.5
[S32]	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0	6.5
[S33]	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	7.0
[S34]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	9.0
[S35]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S36]	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0	6.5
[S37]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S38]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	7.5
[S39]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	9.0
[S40]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S41]	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.0	6.5
[S42]	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S43]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S44]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	7.5
[S45]	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	9.5
[S46]	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	6.5
[S47]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	7.5
[S48]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S49]	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	9.0
[S50]	1.0	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	0.5	1.0	1.0	8.0
[S51]	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.0	6.5
Total	51.0	50.5	46.0	36.5	31.0	6.5	43.0	28.0	45.0	51.0	388.5
Average	1.00	0.99	0.90	0.72	0.61	0.13	0.84	0.55	0.88	1.00	7.62

Table 6: Detailed score for the quality assessment of selected studies.

with regard to the criterion of the existence of a control group with which to compare results). Coverage of this would have been needed to improve scores in the quality assessment.

3.3. Types of Interface Used (RQ1)

The first research question posed in this study addressed the types of interface used in human-machine interaction. In all, 14 different types were found in the items selected. These were the following: Augmented Reality Interface (ARI), Gesture-based Interface (GBI), Gaze-based Interface (GZI), Haptic Human-machine Interface (HHMI), Intelligent User Interface (IUI), Movement-based Interface (MBI), Multimodal User Interface (MUI), Natural User Interface (NUI), Socially Assistive Robot (SAR), Sketch-based Interface (SBI), Surface-based Interface (SUI), Tendon-based Haptic Interface (TBHI), Tangible User Interface (TUI) and Wearable User Interface (WUI).

The distribution of these types may be seen in the following diagram.

Figure 7: Distribution of the studies over type of interface.

Among the interfaces listed above, HHMI, NUI and GBI the three most often

used and together represent 53% of the pieces of work chosen, as illustrated in Figure 7. This was to be expected, as the search strings employed in the corresponding phase of the review (see Section 2.2) included terms like “haptic interfaces” and “natural user interface”.

It was also noteworthy that in three of the items chosen (in other words 6% of the total) no type of interface was described. This was either because they were reviews of human-robot interaction or because they were putting forward general guidelines for haptic interactions.

Another interesting aspect of the present study was knowledge of which contexts or fields made use of the various types of interface. This was because, although the review concentrated primarily on the field of HRI, results of interest were found in other fields or applications, as mentioned in Section 3.1. Table 7 shows the various different domains emerging from the items selected in the review.

With regard to the second part of the research question, relative to which interfaces are most widely utilized in HRI, it can be observed from Figure 8 that the two most commonly used are Haptic Human-Machine Interfaces (HHMI) and Natural User Interfaces (NUI). This provided support for the aims of the present study, which was intended to verify the benefits of using natural interfaces in the context of HRI that employ haptic devices.

DOMAIN / USER TYPE	No. STUDIES
Robotic surgery	2
Interaction with mobile devices	1
Control of mobile platforms	2
Interaction with real-world objects	5
Virtual Environment	7
Human-environment Interactions	4
Human-robot Interaction	17
Robot control	4
Freehand gesture input	2
Videogames	1
Mobile Assistive Robots	1
Ubiquitous Computing Environments	1
Physics-based Character Animation	1
Human-computer Interaction	1
Haptics Virtual Learning Systems	1
Rehabilitation	1

Table 7: Domain or user type reported in the selected studies.

Figure 8: Distribution of type of interface in HRI.

3.4. Improvements in the Interfaces Used (RQ2)

In addressing the second research question, relating to how interfaces might be improved so that HRI would be more effective, the first step was to look at the improvements that researchers themselves proposed. Initial investigation revealed that in ten of the items the improvements proposed effectively were evaluations of the design of the system or prototype, since there had either been no assessment testing at all or the system had been evaluated only by the designers themselves and not by any users. These proposals ran from implementing a qualitative usability test (in items S14, S26 and S46) to studies of haptic devices (S08 and S09), via implementation of new working frameworks and scenarios (S18, S33, S43 and S48) for testing prototypes developed. It was also discovered that in three items no description was given of any method for

evaluating usability (S08, S09 and S33).

Consequently, it would appear to be of interest to consider the various evaluation methods used. These may be classified into the following forms:

- *User testing* Fu and Cenk (2012). This comprises systematic observation under controlled conditions to see how users can utilize a given product or service. Although results may sometimes be recorded in a more or less informal way, this is a technique that can easily incorporate measurements to formalize tests.
- *Case study* Yin (2008). This consists of empirical research investigating a present-day phenomenon within its real-life context when the dividing lines between the phenomenon to be assessed and its context are not particularly evident and for which multiple sources of evidence are brought into play.
- *Experimental or user evaluation* Shaw (2003). This involves gathering data experimentally, using real examples, but not as in case studies or controlled experiments, since in this instance results are collected informally.
- *User surveys* Ciolkowski et al. (2003). A survey is an empirical research strategy for compiling information from heterogeneous sources, so that the results obtained from such exercises often have a high level of external validity.
- *Performance test* Weyuker and Vokolos (2000). This is a non-functional test consisting of a process in which the efficiency of a prototype or device is determined through quantitative trials carried out under laboratory conditions. It can also measure qualitative attributes like usability, reliability, scalability and interoperability. In this sort of test, the results may be collected in a formal or informal way, depending on whether the scoring of the test is calibrated against a norm or criterion.

Consideration of all the items chosen revealed that the most frequently used method was experimental or user evaluation, at 45%. This was followed by the case study method, at 33%. The remaining methods may be seen in Table 8 below.

Type of evaluation	No. studies	Percent
User Test	2	3.9%
Case Study	17	33.3%
Experimental/User Evaluation	23	45.1%
User Surveys	4	7.8%
Performance Test	2	3.9%
None	3	5.9%

Table 8: Different evaluation approaches used in the selected papers.

Another sort of improvement proposed by authors of studies selected lay in the incorporation of some further kind of interaction into the initially designed prototypes, so as to enhance their usability (items S05, S10, S11, S15, S20, S27, S30, S37, S42 and S47). The authors of these items themselves propose the development of such improvements in future work. This was because in most instances they would entail a significant change in the design of the prototype described in the original piece of work and of the corresponding interface.

It was also observed that some pieces of work suggested expansion of utilization of their user interface to multiple users who might act within the same workspace (items S16, S23 and S31) or employ the same haptic device (items S17, S19 and S21). This change in the design would bring with it enhanced usability for the user interface concerned, as well as improvements in the design of the virtual scenario where the device is included.

These proposals should be considered in a method of evaluating the usability of the interfaces used in HRI when haptic devices are used, if the effectiveness of these interfaces is to be improved.

3.5. Benefits of Using Natural Interfaces (RQ3)

Finally, when it came to answering the third research question, relating to the benefits that might accrue from the use of natural interfaces in HRI, the study revealed that employing natural interfaces provides improved support for the style of interaction that users themselves prefer. As was stated by Villaroman et al. (2011) in his paper delivered at SIGITE '11, the 2011 Conference on Information Technology Education, 95% -100 % of users prefer multimodal interactions through this sort of interface to other kinds of interaction in which only one source was used for data entry, especially in teaching and learning environments.

When the items chosen were looked at in more detail, as was seen in the previous section, it became clear that in many instances interaction could be improved simply by providing a further channel for data entry or perception. The more channels a system has, the more natural user interactions will be with the device designed for a virtual environment. Moreover, an enhanced reality component could be added that would permit users to view in real time the data needed for interaction.

However, when it comes to implementing this sort of improvement, various problems arise. Perhaps the most important is the question of response times. It is obvious that if a multimodal system is in use, with several different devices receiving and transmitting signals, there will be latency and a need to synchronize these signals (items S02 and S03).

A further problem is achieving an appropriate virtual working environment in which all the forms of perception employed in the natural user interface can be processed correctly, so as to ensure the most reliable results possible (items S25, S34, S38 and S39). In some cases, there would be a need to adapt the prototype itself to the working environment and to carry out fresh assessment tests (items S07, S17, S35, S49, S47 and S51).

In the specific instance of the items chosen in which haptic devices were used for HRI, it would appear possible to improve the interfaces designed by their authors by adding further forms of interaction compatible with the sense of

touch. An example would be the use of 3-D vision devices, such as monitors or stereoscopic glasses (item S44). It would also be possible to consider including the use of facial expressions or spoken commands to transmit information, complementing the employment of gestures in human-robot interaction (items S22, S23, S28 and S47).

On these lines, systems could be implemented to aid communication between humans and robots utilizing natural interfaces (item S10). This would facilitate the use of robots to help people with accessibility problems (items S13, S46 and S49) and be of assistance in rehabilitation tasks (items S18 and S44). It would also be very useful in controlled teaching and learning environments, in fields like surgery (items S01 and S21) and in the area of education (items S35, S39 and S45).

For all these reasons, it may be concluded that the employment of natural user interfaces significantly improves HRI when haptic devices are brought into play. It may also in some instances contribute to mitigating the limitations on use of such devices.

4. Limitation of this review

This systematic review has certain limitations. Firstly, because the study covered a fixed period of some ten years, it could not guarantee that all relevant work would be chosen. Although searches were performed in all the main digital libraries in the field of HRI, it is possible that some research of value was omitted in the searching process.

Secondly, despite the search strings used being extensive, it is possible that they did not cover some relevant items. An attempt was made to compensate for this limitation by extending searches to the bibliographic references in the primary studies picked out during the first selection phase (see Figure 3) so as to find further work that might be considered relevant for this study.

A further weakness relating to search strings is that the first trawl threw up a large number of documents, some of them duplicated because they came

from different digital libraries. This fact required a great deal of time and effort to resolve, so an attempt was made to limit the time spent reviewing each source and to split the work between two researchers, so as in this way to reduce human error arising from fatigue. Once the task was completed, the outcomes were shared, and in cases of disagreement a third opinion was taken into account.

It is also important to stress, as mentioned in Section 2.2.2 of this paper, that the search processes in the electronic libraries used are not exactly alike. Hence, it proved necessary to adapt the search strings for each library, while attempting to ensure they were equivalent so as to achieve consistent results.

Thirdly, since only publications written in English were included, it is possible that relevant publications have been excluded because they were from research groups and professional journals from countries that publish HRI work in other languages.

Finally, during the process of extracting and analysing data items were classified on the basis of researcher judgements. This means that some pieces of work may have been wrongly classified. With an eye to mitigating this risk, the coding process was always done by two researchers working independently, with a third researcher brought in in cases of disagreement.

5. Conclusions and future work

The goal of this systematic review was to investigate the use of natural interfaces in the context of HRI when haptic devices are involved. An extensive search of the literature was undertaken with the aim of selecting relevant papers and pieces of work related to the topic of the review that had been published over a period running from 2004 to 2014. In the end 51 articles were chosen as related to the three research questions posed at the start of the review. The main outcomes from this review are summarized below.

- (RQ1) A total of 14 different types of interface were identified as in use in human-machine interaction, the commonest being Haptic Human-Machine

Interfaces (HHMI) at 25%, Natural User Interfaces (NUI) at 17% and Gesture-Based Interfaces at 15%. In the field of human-robot interaction the most widely used were the first two (HHMI and NUI).

- (RQ2) Improvements proposed so that interfaces utilized in human-robot interaction would be more effective concentrated primarily on methods for assessing the usability of prototypes. Among such methods, the most frequently used was the experimental or user evaluation method, amounting to 45%. Another prominent proposal was to make use of more than one sort of interaction, which entails the utilization of multi-modal interfaces.
- (RQ3) Using natural interfaces in the context of human-robot interaction implies a major enhancement, especially when haptic devices are brought into play, since, as stated previously, this increases the number of channels for interaction with users.

The greatest problem encountered during the course of the study was the difficulty of assessing the usability of interfaces employed, especially when they brought into play more than one type of interaction with users (multimodal user interfaces). It was precisely this sort of interface that was of particular interest for this work, because it provides a more natural way of interacting with users in controlled learning environments.

However, efficiency is not one of the strong points of multimodal interfaces, as was shown by Dumas et al. (2009) in his study. It is thus necessary to improve the efficacy of design of this sort of interface. To achieve this aim there is a need to use a methodology that will allow evaluation of the usability of an interface from the earliest stages in its design, so as to avoid any requirement to redesign the interface when its prototype is already at an advanced stage of development.

Furthermore, it has been shown that multimodal interfaces enhance the control of errors and reliability. According to Dumas himself, users make 36% fewer mistakes with multimodal, as opposed to unimodal interfaces.

There would not appear to be any generic standard or re-usable assessment method that would exhaustively define parameters permitting the evaluation of haptic interfaces in the context of HRI.

Our future work is focused on creating a methodology for evaluating natural interfaces in HRI by means of prototypes that use haptic devices as their main interaction channel.

Appendix A. Bibliographic details of the papers that were assessed using quality assessment criteria.

- [S01] Iñaki Díaz, Jorge Juan Gil, and Marcos Louredo. A haptic pedal for surgery assistance. *Computer methods and programs in biomedicine*, 116(2):97 – 104, 2014. New methods of human-robot interaction in medical practice.
- [S02] Jerome Pasquero, Scott J. Stobbe, and Noel Stonehouse. A haptic wristwatch for eyes-free interactions. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, CHI '11*, pages 3257-3266, New York, NY, USA, 2011.
- [S03] Andrea Sanna, Fabrizio Lamberti, Gianluca Paravati, and Federico Manuri. A kinect-based natural interface for quadrotor control. *Entertainment Computing*, 4(3):179 – 186, 2013.
- [S04] M. Nakao, R. Kitamura, T. Sato, and K. Minato. A model for sharing haptic interaction. *Haptics, IEEE Transactions on*, 3(4):292–296, Oct 2010.
- [S05] ThomasB. Moeslund, Moritz String, and Erik Granum. A natural interface to a virtual environment through computer vision-estimated pointing gestures. In Ipke Wachsmuth and Timo Sowa, editors, *Gesture and Sign Language in Human-Computer Interaction*, volume 2298 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 59–63. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2002.

- [S06] Joachim von Zitzewitz, Andre Morger, Georg Rauter, Laura Marchal-Crespo, Francesco Crivelli, Dario Wyss, Tobias Bruckmann, and Robert Riener. A reconfigurable, tendon-based haptic interface for research into human-environment interactions. *Robotica*, 31:441–453, 5 2013.
- [S07] D. Shah, J. Schneider, and M. Campbell. A sketch interface for robust and natural robot control. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 100(3):604–622, March 2012.
- [S08] Ferran Argelaguet and Carlos Andujar. A survey of 3d object selection techniques for virtual environments. *Computers & Graphics*, 37(3):121 – 136, 2013.
- [S09] Brenna D. Argall and Aude G. Billard. A survey of tactile human–robot interactions. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, 58(10):1159 – 1176, 2010.
- [S10] Jinglin Shen and N. Gans. A trifocal tensor based camera-projector system for robot-human interaction. In *Robotics and Biomimetics (ROBIO), 2012 IEEE International Conference on*, pages 1110–1116, Dec 2012.
- [S11] J. Sugiyama and J. Miura. A wearable robot control interface based on measurement of human body motion using a camera and inertial sensors. In *Robotics and Biomimetics (ROBIO), 2011 IEEE International Conference on*, pages 565–570, Dec 2011.
- [S12] E. Torta, J. Oberzaucher, F. Werner, R.H. Cuijpers, and J.F. Juola. Attitudes towards socially assistive robots in intelligent homes: Results from laboratory studies and field trials. In *Journal of Human-Robot Interaction*, volume 1, pages 76–99, 2012.
- [S13] Geunho Lee, Takanori Ohnuma, and NakYoung Chong. Design and control of jaist active robotic walker. *Intelligent Service Robotics*, 3(3):125–135, 2010.

- [S14] L.M. Muñoz, P. Ponsa, and A. Casals. Design and development of a guideline for ergonomic haptic interaction. In ZdzislawS. Hippe, JuliuszL. Kulikowski, and Teresa Mroczek, editors, *Human – Computer Systems Interaction: Backgrounds and Applications 2*, volume 99 of *Advances in Intelligent and Soft Computing*, pages 15–29. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2012.
- [S15] Tao Ni, Doug A. Bowman, Chris North, and Ryan P. McMahan. Design and evaluation of freehand menu selection interfaces using tilt and pinch gestures. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 69(9):551 – 562, 2011.
- [S16] Mark Micire, Munjal Desai, Jill L. Drury, Eric McCann, Adam Norton, Katherine M. Tsui, and Holly A. Yanco. Design and validation of two- handed multi-touch tabletop controllers for robot teleoperation. In *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces, IUI '11*, pages 145–154, New York, NY, USA, 2011.
- [S17] Zoran Najdovski, Saeid Nahavandi, and Toshio Fukuda. Design development, and evaluation of a pinch-grasp haptic interface. *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, 19(1):45-54, 2014.
- [S18] Danilo Avola, Matteo Spezialetti, and Giuseppe Placidi. Design of an ecient framework for fast prototyping of customized human-computer interfaces and virtual environments for rehabilitation. *Comput. Methods Prog. Biomed.*, 110(3):490-502, June 2013.
- [S19] T. Endo, S. Tanimura, and H. Kawasaki. Development of tool-type devices for a multingered haptic interface robot. *Robotics, IEEE Transactions on*, 29(1):68-81, Feb 2013.

- [S20] Luís Filipe Teófilo, Pedro Alves Nogueira, and Pedro Brandao Silva. GEMINI: A generic multi-modal natural interface framework for videogames. In Alvaro Rocha, Ana Maria Correia, Tom Wilson, and Karl A. Stroetmann, editors, *Advances in Information Systems and Technologies*, volume 206 of *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, pages 873–884. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2013.
- [S21] Rong Wen, Wei-Liang Tay, Binh P. Nguyen, Chin-Boon Chng, and Chee-Kong Chui. Hand gesture guided robot-assisted surgery based on a direct augmented reality interface. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, 116(2):68 – 80, 2014. *New methods of human-robot interaction in medical practice*.
- [S22] Huanran Wang and X.P. Liu. Haptic interaction for mobile assistive robots. *Instrumentation and Measurement, IEEE Transactions on*, 60(11):3501–3509, Nov 2011.
- [S23] Vladimir Kulyukin. Human-robot interaction through gesture-free spoken dialogue. *Autonomous Robots*, 16(3):239–257, 2004.
- [S24] Sean Gustafson, Daniel Bierwirth, and Patrick Baudisch. Imaginary interfaces: Spatial interaction with empty hands and without visual feedback. In *Proceedings of the 23Nd Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology, UIST '10*, pages 3–12, New York, NY, USA, 2010. ACM.
- [S25] Chiew Seng Sean Tan, Johannes Schöning, Kris Luyten, and Karin Coninx. Informing intelligent user interfaces by inferring affective states from body postures in ubiquitous computing environments. In *Proceedings of the 2013 International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces, IUI '13*, pages 235–246, New York, NY, USA, 2013.
- [S26] Werner A. König, Roman Rädle, and Harald Reiterer. Interactive design of multimodal user interfaces. *Journal on Multimodal User Interfaces*, 3(3):197–213, 2010.

- [S27] Christopher Peters, Stylianos Asteriadis, and Kostas Karpouzis. Investigating shared attention with a virtual agent using a gaze-based interface. *Journal on Multimodal User Interfaces*, 3(1-2):119–130, 2010.
- [S28] Luka Peternel and Jan Babic. Learning of compliant human–robot interaction using full-body haptic interface. *Advanced Robotics*, 27(13):1003–1012, 2013.
- [S29] J.M. Romano and K.J. Kuchenbecker. Methods for robotic tool-mediated haptic surface recognition. In *Haptics Symposium (HAPTICS), 2014 IEEE*, pages 49–56, Feb 2014.
- [S30] Francois Ferland, Dominic Létourneau, Arnaud Aumont, Julien Frémy, Marc-Antoine Legault, Michel Lauria, and Francois Michaud. Natural interaction design of a humanoid robot. *Journal of Human-Robot Interaction*, 1(2), 2013.
- [S31] E. Sato, T. Yamaguchi, and F. Harashima. Natural interface using pointing behavior for human-robot gestural interaction. *Industrial Electronics, IEEE Transactions on*, 54(2):1105–1112, April 2007.
- [S32] A. Ozgur, S. Bonardi, M. Vespignani, R. Mockel, and A.J. Ijspeert. Natural user interface for roombots. In *Robot and Human Interactive Communication, 2014 RO-MAN: The 23rd IEEE International Symposium on*, pages 12–17, Aug 2014.
- [S33] C. Karen Liu and Victor B. Zordan. Natural user interface for physics-based character animation. In *Motion in Games*, volume 7060 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 1–14. 2011.
- [S34] Guanyang Liu and Keke Lu. Networked multiplayer cooperative interaction using decoupled motion control method in a shared virtual environment with haptic, visual and movementfeedback. *Computer Animation and Virtual Worlds*, 24(2):97–109, 2013.

- [S35] D.J. Christensen, R. Fogh, and H.H. Lund. Playte, a tangible interface for engaging human-robot interaction. In *Robot and Human Interactive 5 Communication, 2014 RO-MAN: The 23rd IEEE International Symposium on*, pages 56-62, Aug 2014.
- [S36] Ankit Dave, Yogesh Bhumkar, Abin Abraham, and Rekha Sugandhi. Project MUDRA: Personalization of computers using natural interface. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 54(17):42-46, September 2012.
- [S37] Shu-Yang Lin, Chao-Huai Su, Kai-Yin Cheng, Rong-Hao Liang, Tzu-Hao Kuo, and Bing-Yu Chen. Pub - point upon body: Exploring eyesfree interaction and methods on an arm. In *Proceedings of the 24th Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology, UIST '11*, pages 481-488, New York, NY, USA, 2011.
- [S38] Chung Hyuk Park and A.M. Howard. Real world haptic exploration for telepresence of the visually impaired. In *Human-Robot Interaction (HRI), 2012 7th ACM/IEEE International Conference on*, pages 65-72, March 2012.
- [S39] Jonathan P. San Diego, Margaret J. Cox, Barry F.A. Quinn, Jonathan Tim Newton, Avijit Banerjee, and Mark Woolford. Researching haptics in higher education: The complexity of developing haptics virtual learning systems and evaluating its impact on students' learning. *Computers & Education*, 59(1):156-166, 2012.
- [S40] Esben Warming Pedersen and Kasper Hornbæk. Tangible bots: Interaction with active tangibles in tabletop interfaces. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, CHI '11*, pages 2975-2984, New York, NY, USA, 2011.
- [S41] Gabriele Randelli, Matteo Venanzi, and Daniele Nardi. Tangible interfaces for robot teleoperation. In *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Human-robot Interaction, HRI '11*, pages 231-232, New York, NY, USA, 2011.

- [S42] Chris Harrison, Julia Schwarz, and Scott E. Hudson. Tapsense: Enhancing nger interaction on touch surfaces. In *Proceedings of the 24th Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology, UIST '11*, pages 627-636, New York, NY, USA, 2011.
- [S43] Anca Dragan, Kenton Lee, and Siddhartha Srinivasa. Teleoperation with intelligent and customizable interfaces. *Journal of Human-Robot Interaction, Special Issue on Technical and Social Advances in HRI*, 1(3), January 2013.
- [S44] V. Bartenbach, C. Sander, M. Pöschl, K. Wilging, T. Nelius, F. Doll, W. Burger, C. Stockinger, A. Focke, and T. Stein. The biomotionbot: A robotic device for applications in human motor learning and rehabilitation. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods*, 213(2):282 – 297, 2013.
- [S45] P. Rouanet, P.Y. Oudeyer, F. Danieau, and D. Filliat. The impact of human-robot interfaces on the learning of visual objects. *Robotics, IEEE Transactions on*, 29(2):525–541, April 2013.
- [S46] S. Yokota, D. Chugo, H. Hashimoto, and K. Kawabata. The personal mobility interface including human twisting motion. In *Robot and Human Interactive Communication, 2014 RO-MAN: The 23rd IEEE International Symposium on*, pages 1–5, Aug 2014.
- [S47] M. Spangenberg and D. Henrich. Towards an intuitive interface for instructing robots handling tasks based on verbalized physical effects. In *Robot and Human Interactive Communication, 2014 RO-MAN: The 23rd IEEE International Symposium on*, pages 79–84, Aug 2014.
- [S48] Tom Carter, Sue Ann Seah, Benjamin Long, Bruce Drinkwater, and Sriram Subramanian. Ultrahaptics: Multi-point mid-air haptic feedback for touch surfaces. In *Proceedings of the 26th Annual ACM Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology, UIST '13*, pages 505–514, New York, NY, USA, 2013. ACM.

- [S49] Marcus Mast, Michael Burmester, Katja Kruger, Sascha Fatikow, Georg Arbeiter, Birgit Graf, Gernot Kronreif, Lucia Pigni, David Facal, and Renxi Qiu. User-centered design of a dynamic-autonomy remote interaction concept for manipulation-capable robots to assist elderly people in the home. *Journal of Human-Robot Interaction*, 1(1), 2012.
- [S50] L. Jiang, M.R. Cutkosky, J. Ruutiainen, and R. Raisamo. Using haptic feedback to improve grasp force control in multiple sclerosis patients. *Robotics, IEEE Transactions on*, 25(3):593–601, June 2009.
- [S51] Oscar Ardaiz, Ernesto Arroyo, Valeria Righi, Oriol Galimany, and Josep Blat. Virtual collaborative environments with distributed multitouch 7 support. In *Proceedings of the 2nd ACM SIGCHI Symposium on Engineering Interactive Computing Systems, EICS '10*, pages 235-240, New York, NY, USA, 2010.

References

- Barreto, F., Benitti, V., 2012. Exploring the educational potential of robotics in schools: A systematic review. *Computers and Education* 58 (3), 978–988.
URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360131511002508>
- Basteris, A., Nijenhuis, S., Stienen, A., Buurke, J., Prange, G., Amirabdollahian, F., 2014. Training modalities in robot-mediated upper limb rehabilitation in stroke: a framework for classification based on a systematic review. *Journal of NeuroEngineering and Rehabilitation* 11 (1).
URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/1743-0003-11-111>
- Bemelmans, R., Gelderblom, G. J., Jonker, P., de Witte, L., 2012. Socially assistive robots in elderly care: A systematic review into effects and effectiveness. *Journal of the American Medical Directors Association* 13 (2), 114 – 120.e1.
URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1525861010003476>

- Brave, S., Dahley, A., 1997. intouch: A medium for haptic interpersonal communication. In: CHI '97 Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems. CHI EA '97. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp. 363–364.
URL <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1120212.1120435>
- Brereton, P., Kitchenham, B., Budgen, D., Turner, M., Khalil, M., 2007. Lessons from applying the systematic literature review process within the software engineering domain. *Journal of Systems and Software* 80 (4), 571 – 583, software Performance 5th International Workshop on Software and Performance.
URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S016412120600197X>
- Chen, L., Babar, M., 2011a. A systematic review of evaluation of variability management approaches in software product lines. *Information and Software Technology* 53 (4), 344 – 362.
URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950584910002223>
- Chen, L., Babar, M. A., 2011b. A systematic review of evaluation of variability management approaches in software product lines. *Information and Software Technology* 53 (4), 344 – 362, special section: Software Engineering track of the 24th Annual Symposium on Applied Computing Software Engineering track of the 24th Annual Symposium on Applied Computing.
URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950584910002223>
- Ciolkowski, M., Laitenberger, O., Vegas, S., Biffel, S., 2003. Practical experiences in the design and conduct of surveys in empirical software engineering. In: Conradi, R., Wang, A. (Eds.), *Empirical Methods and Studies in Software Engineering*. Vol. 2765 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 104–128.
URL http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-45143-3_7

- Conn, V., Valentine, J., Cooper, H., Rantz, M., 2003. Grey literature in meta-analyses. *Nursing research* 52 (4), 256–261.
URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/00006199-200307000-00008>
- Cooper, H. M., 1988. Organizing knowledge syntheses: A taxonomy of literature reviews. *Knowledge in Society* 1 (1), 104–126.
URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF03177550>
- Dautenhahn, K., 2007. Methodology and themes of human-robot interaction: a growing research field. *International Journal of Advanced Robotic Systems* 4 (1), 103–108.
URL <http://www.intechweb.org/journal.php?id=3>
- Dickersin, K., Scherer, R., Lefebvre, C., 1994. Identifying relevant studies for systematic reviews. *British Medical Journal* 309 (6964), 1286–1291.
- Dieste, O., Padua, O., Sept 2007. Developing search strategies for detecting relevant experiments for systematic reviews. In: *Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement, 2007. ESEM 2007. First International Symposium on*. pp. 215–224.
- Dumas, B., Lalanne, D., Oviatt, S., 2009. Multimodal interfaces: A survey of principles, models and frameworks. In: Lalanne, D., Kohlas, J. (Eds.), *Human Machine Interaction*. Vol. 5440 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 3–26.
URL http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-00437-7_1
- Dybå, T., Dingsøy, T., 2008a. Empirical studies of agile software development: A systematic review. *Information and Software Technology* 50 (9–10), 833 – 859.
URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950584908000256>
- Dybå, T., Dingsøy, T., 2008b. Empirical studies of agile software development: A systematic review. *Information and Software Technology* 50 (9–10), 833 –

859.

URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950584908000256>

Dybå, T., Dingsøy, T., Hanssen, G., Sept 2007. Applying systematic reviews to diverse study types: An experience report. In: Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement, 2007. ESEM 2007. First International Symposium on. pp. 225–234.

Fu, M. J., Cenk, C. M., 2012. Human-arm-and-hand-dynamic model with variability analyses for a stylus-based haptic interface. IEEE transactions on systems, man, and cybernetics. Part B, Cybernetics : a publication of the IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Society 42 (6), 1633–44.

Gonzalo Esteban, Camino Fernández, M. A. C. V. M., May/June 2015. Learning systems through haptic simulators - a domain expertise approach. International Journal of Engineering Education 31-3, 726–735.

Haans, A., de Nood, C., IJsselsteijn, W., 2007. Investigating response similarities between real and mediated social touch: A first test. In: CHI '07 Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems. CHI EA '07. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp. 2405–2410.
URL <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/1240866.1241015>

Haans, A., IJsselsteijn, W., Jan. 2006. Mediated social touch: A review of current research and future directions. Virtual Real. 9 (2), 149–159.
URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10055-005-0014-2>

Jorgensen, M., Shepperd, M., Jan 2007. A systematic review of software development cost estimation studies. Software Engineering, IEEE Transactions on 33 (1), 33–53.

Jørgensen, M., 2004. A review of studies on expert estimation of software development effort. Journal of Systems and Software 70 (1–2), 37 – 60.

- URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0164121202001565>
- Kitchenham, B., Brereton, O. P., Budgen, D., Turner, M., Bailey, J., Linkman, S., 2009. Systematic literature reviews in software engineering – a systematic literature review. *Information and Software Technology* 51 (1), 7 – 15, special Section - Most Cited Articles in 2002 and Regular Research Papers.
- URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950584908001390>
- Kitchenham, B., Pretorius, R., Budgen, D., Brereton, O. P., Turner, M., Niazi, M., Linkman, S., 2010. Systematic literature reviews in software engineering – a tertiary study. *Information and Software Technology* 52 (8), 792 – 805.
- URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950584910000467>
- Lincoln, Y., Guba, E., 1985. *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Sage focus editions. SAGE Publications.
- URL <http://books.google.es/books?id=2oA9aWlNeoC>
- Matellán, V., Fernández, C., 2014. What downgrades a robot form a pet to appliance? *Interaction Studies* 15 (2), 210–215.
- Montuschi, P., Sanna, A., Lamberti, F., Paravati, G., Sept 2014. Human-computer interaction: Present and future trends. *Computing Now* 7 (9).
- URL <http://www.computer.org/web/computingnow/archive/september2014>
- Orwin, R., Vevea, J., 2009. Evaluating coding decisions. *The handbook of research synthesis and meta-analysis* 2, 177–203.
- Pautasso, M., 07 2013. Ten simple rules for writing a literature review. *PLoS Comput Biol* 9 (7), e1003149.
- URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1003149>

Prewett, M. S., Johnson, R. C., Saboe, K. N., Elliott, L. R., Coovert, M. D., 2010. Managing workload in human–robot interaction: A review of empirical studies. *Computers in Human Behavior* 26 (5), 840 – 856, advancing Educational Research on Computer-supported Collaborative Learning (CSCL) through the use of gStudy {CSCL} Tools.

URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0747563210000506>

Riek, L., 2012. Wizard of oz studies in hri: A systematic review and new reporting guidelines. *Journal of Human-Robot Interaction*, 119–136.

Salter, T., Dautenhahn, K., Boekhorst, R., 2006. Learning about natural human–robot interaction styles. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems* 54 (2), 127 – 134, intelligent Autonomous Systems 8th Conference on Intelligent Autonomous Systems (IAS-8).

URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S092188900500151X>

Sandford, P., 1996. Completeness of reporting of trials published in languages other than english. *The Lancet* 347 (9005), 907 – 908.

URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0140673696913938>

Seaman, C., Jul 1999. Qualitative methods in empirical studies of software engineering. *Software Engineering, IEEE Transactions on* 25 (4), 557–572.

Shaw, M., 2003. Writing good software engineering research papers: Minitutorial. In: *Proceedings of the 25th International Conference on Software Engineering, ICSE '03*. IEEE Computer Society, Washington, DC, USA, pp. 726–736.

URL <http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=776816.776925>

Srinivasan, M. A., Basdogan, C., 1997. Haptics in virtual environments: Taxonomy, research status, and challenges. *Computers & Graphics* 21 (4),

393–404.

URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0097849397000307>

Stiefelhagen, R., Fugen, C., Giesemann, R., Holzapfel, H., Nickel, K., Waibel, A., 2004. Natural human-robot interaction using speech, head pose and gestures. In: in Meetings with Omnidirectional Cameras, International workshop on Multimedia Technologies in E-learning and Collaboration.

Tramèr, M., Reynolds, D., Moore, R., McQuay, H., 1997. Impact of covert duplicate publication on meta-analysis: a case study. *BMJ* 315 (7109), 635–640.

Tsetserukou, D., 2010. Haptihug: A novel haptic display for communication of hug over a distance. In: Proceedings of the 2010 International Conference on Haptics: Generating and Perceiving Tangible Sensations, Part I. EuroHaptics'10. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 340–347.
URL <http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=1884164.1884216>

Villaroman, N., Rowe, D., Swan, B., 2011. Teaching natural user interaction using openni and the microsoft kinect sensor. In: Proceedings of the 2011 Conference on Information Technology Education. SIGITE '11. ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp. 227–232.
URL <http://doi.acm.org/10.1145/2047594.2047654>

Wen, J., Li, S., Lin, Z., Hu, Y., Huang, C., 2012. Systematic literature review of machine learning based software development effort estimation models. *Information and Software Technology* 54 (1), 41 – 59.
URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950584911001832>

Weyuker, E., Vokolos, F., Dec 2000. Experience with performance testing of software systems: issues, an approach, and case study. *Software Engineering, IEEE Transactions on* 26 (12), 1147–1156.

Yin, R. K., Oct 2008. Case study research: Design and methods. In: Applied Social Research Methods. SAGE Publications, Inc.

Zhang, H., Babar, M., 2013. Systematic reviews in software engineering: An empirical investigation. Information and Software Technology 55 (7), 1341 – 1354.

URL <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950584912002029>